

The Sociological Perspective of Discrimination towards Andrew Beckett in *Philadelphia* Movie

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of the research is to describe discrimination of Andrew Beckett and his struggle against discrimination in his work groups, and society. The object of this research is the character of Andrew Beckett in *Philadelphia* Movie. The researchers fit the correlational research method to apply their research. The variables data between discrimination and sociological perspective are connected each other. The results of the research are: (1) the character of Andrew Beckett is protagonist character who struggle to get his right, patient, excellent lawyer and loving his family; (2) the problems is discrimination of Andrew Beckett who infected AIDS and a gay that happens in social services, and in the work place; (3) the struggle of Andrew Beckett in the movie is about to prove the discrimination, to get a lawyer and get over from AIDS.

KEYWORDS –AIDS, Discrimination, Sociological Perspective

I. INTRODUCTION

Movie is one of the literary arts that can realize the form can be enjoyed. A movie often illustrates the situation of the social condition of the people in a certain time. A movie can encourage an empathy and tolerance. It can make the audience know themselves through the figures or the characters in the story. A movie is often made to be used as the manifestation of life. One of the studies that can analyze the real life in a movie is sociology.

Sociology is the scientific study of society, including patterns of social relationships, social interaction, and culture. One of the most common problem in society is about discrimination. In human social affairs, discrimination is treatment or consideration of, or making a distinction in favour of or against, a person based on the group, class, or category to which the person is perceived to belong. These include sexual orientation, gender identity, religion, disability, and many others.

The phenomena of discrimination happened in *Philadelphia* movie which tells about Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS). The story told about Andrew Beckett (Tom Hanks), who contracted AIDS and got fired from the prestigious Wyant Wheeler law firm because of the illness. One of the factors that make researchers were interested on this research was to contribute to the World AIDS day. People who lived with AIDS on their body should deal with discrimination circumstances especially in workplace. This situation can be proved with previous research which entitle Employment Discrimination and HIV Stigma: survey result from civil society organisations and people living with HIV in Africa that said the findings of global and regional surveys indicate the existence of high levels of employment discrimination based on HIV status worldwide, including forced disclosure of HIV status, exclusion in the workplace, refusals to hire or promote, and terminations of people known to be living with HIV.

Another factor the researchers choose *Philadelphia* movie as the topic of their research because the movie brought a good message to everyone who watches it. This movie shows how people with AIDS are discriminated and how AIDS infects others, how they struggle to get their right. Besides, this movie can clarify the misconceptions in social reality life about the disease (AIDS), about those who contract it, and about gay community in general. The problems that are encountered on the discussion of this article are:

(1) How are the characteristic of discrimination of Andrew Beckett described and his struggle against discrimination?

(2) How are the discrimination connected to sociological perspective?

II. METHODS

Related to this research, researchers use correlational research which is the same with descriptive research as explained by Geoffrey Marczyk that is useful because it can provide important information regarding the average member of a group. In correlational research, the researcher attempts to determine whether there is a relationship – that is, correlation – between two or more variables, (Marczyk, 2005). On this case, the researchers try to relate between discrimination and sociological perspective toward one character that is *Andrew Beckett*. The variables in correlational research are sometimes called explanatory or predictor variables instead of independent variables because they are not experimentally manipulated. The dependent variable is then termed the outcome or criterion variable, (Mertens, 2019).

The data used dialogues in *Philadelphia* movie as a form of discrimination of Andrew Beckett using sociological perspective. The researchers took the theories that supported information related to discrimination and sociological perspective from e-book and some journals. The whole research is elaborate through words, including the explanation of data analysis and interpretation of results or findings. To strengthen this method, the researchers also derived a theory from Denzin regarding to sociological method that the sociological discipline rests on these elements: theory, methodology, research activity, and sociological imagination. The sociological imagination in considerable part of the capacity of shift from one perspective to another, and in the process to build up an adequate view of total society and its components, (Denzin, 1978).

III. FINDINGS

3.1. Discrimination of Andrew Beckett

According to (Acas, 2017) “The Equality Act defines nine protected characteristics from discrimination”. This movie at least tells two characteristics of discrimination, they are discrimination of AIDS disease and discrimination of sexual orientation (Gay).

3.1.1. Discrimination of AIDS Disease

In that time, people did not get enough information about AIDS. People had bad assumption about AIDS and people who are infected. Because of that they make their own assumption about the disease. They assumed that the virus can travel through the air, for examples: by breathing the same air in the same room or touching. That was why they avoid the HIV victims.

Their assumption about the disease is a big mistake just because shaking hands, or hugging, using the same toilet, even kissing someone, it cannot transmit AIDS.

Dr. Armbruster : The HIV virus can only be transmitted through the exchange of bodily fluids, namely blood, semen and vagina fluid.

Joe : Right. Yeah. Thanks for your information.

(Hospital, 00:32:39-00: 32:42)

The dialogue above happens when Joe comes to the hospital and he meet Dr. Armbruster and ask about HIV transmission. It explains how the virus infects the others, that HIV virus only can be transmitted through some actions that involve the exchange of body fluids, namely blood, semen and vagina fluid. Some actions to be avoided are unprotected sex, blood transfusion, etc. Here are some scenes of discrimination that happens in this movie:

i. In Social Service (accommodation, goods and service)

Librarian : This is the supplement. You're right, there is a section on... HIV related discrimination.

Andrew : Thank you.

Librarian : We do have a private research room available.
Andrew : I'm fine right here, thank you.
Librarian : Wouldn't you be more comfortable in a research room?
Andrew : (pleasantly) No, would it make you more comfortable?

(Library, 00:31:40-00:35:02)

It can be seen that the librarian insists on Andrew to move to the other room and a man in the same table with Andrew, moved away after he heard the conversation between Andrew and the librarian. They avoid Andrew because of their fear of AIDS.

The bad perception about the HIV virus causes misconception in the society. People do not want to seat in the same table or chair with the AIDS victims. That is kind of discrimination. The setting of this scene takes place in the library which is a public accommodation that everyone can freely access without any discrimination.

ii. In the work place

Joe : What can I do for you?
Andrew : I've been fired by Wyant, Wheeler. I want to bring a wrongful Termination suit against Wheeler.
Joe : You want to sue Wyant, Wheeler?
Andrew : Correct, I'm seeking representation.
Joe : Continue.
Andrew : I misplaced an important complaint. The night before it was due, I worked on the complaint in my office. I left a copy of it on my desk. The next day, the complaint vanished. No hard copy. All traces of it mysteriously gone from my computer. Miraculously, a copy of the complaint was located at the last minute. And we got it to court on time. But the next day I was summoned to meeting with the managing partners. They were waiting for me in the conference room. And I was fired.
Joe : And then...
Andrew : From the day they hired me to the day I was fired...I served my clients consistently, thoroughly, with absolute excellence. If they hadn't fired me, that's what I'd be doing today.
Joe : And they don't want to fire you because for having AIDS. So. In spite of your brilliance, they make you look incompetent. Thus, the mysterious lost files. Is that what you're trying to tell me?
Andrew : Correct. I was sabotaged.

(Joe's office, 00:22:50-00:26:55)

From the dialogue above Andrew suing his office because he believes that he is fired because he infected AIDS. So, Andrew comes to Joe's office and asks Joe to be his lawyer and tell Joe what caused him to be fired.

It is clearly seen that Andrew's boss fired him because they were afraid of AIDS and they sabotaged Andrew with the lost file that they had planned and it became the reason to fire Andrew. And the scene below supports the discrimination of Andrew.

Wheeler : Andrew brought AIDS into our offices...
Kenton : We ought to sue him.

(Office, 00:39:50-00:39:59)

Wheeler and Kenton are Andrew's partners in the firm. From the dialogues above, the researchers conclude that the discrimination in this movie happens in work place also, Andrew's partners who hate AIDS, wanted to fire him. They did not have compassion towards AIDS infected person.

3.2. Discrimination of Gay

Like AIDS victims, gay is also discriminated by society. Some dialogues shows the discrimination of gay people as follows:

3.2.1. In social service

Filko : You're noy getting a little light in the sneakers, are you pal?
Joe : Yeah, I am changing. I'm on the prowl, Filko. I need a hunk, a hunk like you. you can tell everybody.
You know what we do. Want to play sailor? Remember? You're the first mate.
Filko : That's not funny.
Joe : Let me tell you something. These people make me sick. But a law's been broken.
(Bar, 00:52:07-00:52:56)

Because of Joe helps Andrew become Andrew's lawyer it affects to him. That scene happens in the bar. Filko is one of Joe's friends tried to make a joke but that joke made Joe angry. It shows how people hate gay people. People consider that homosexuality as deviation. People are afraid of homosexuality because they bring bad impact to the environment, to themselves and to children. Some people think that gay is disgusting.

3.2.2. In the work place

Joe : you had one guy "like that". You mean a homosexual?
Kenton : he. Uh..., strutted around quarters naked trying to get everybody to notice him, made everyone sick.
It was destroying our morale. So, we let him know this kind of behavior was not acceptable.
Joe : How'd you do that, what, you wrote him a letter?
Kenton : We stuck his head in a latrine after ten of us had used it.
Joe : Ah, you taught him a lesson, didn't you?
Kenton : Yes, we did.
Joe : Just like firing Andrew Beckett taught him a lesson.
(Court room, 01:05:30-01:06:04)

Kenton is Andrew's partner in the firm. The conversation above when Kenton becomes a witness in the trial and Joe asks him some questions. From the dialogue above, Homosexual is treated badly by some people. Some people like to torture gays. And we can see that homosexual is not only discriminated but is also hated by some people.

For most people, homosexual is an unacceptable attitude. They consider homosexuality as a disease. That is why gays never show themselves in front of the society. Especially, after they find out about other people's opinion about homosexual. They prefer to keep in silence. Here is the scene that shows why Andrew is silent about his sexual orientation:

Joe : So, in the years you worked at Wyant Wheeler, did you ever tell Charles Wheeler you were gay?
Andrew : No, I didn't
Joe : Why not?
Andrew : You do not bring your personal life into a law firm. You're not supposed to have a personal life, really. Anyway, I did plan to tell Charles eventually, but then this, oh, something happened at the racquet club about 3 years ago... somebody started telling some jokes."
(Flash back sequence, In Spa room.)
Wheeler : Hey, Walter, how does a faggot fake an orgasm?
Walter : He throws a quart of hot yogurt on your back.
(Andrew continue talking)
Andrew : Relieved. That I never told him I was a gay.
(Court room, 01:24:00-01:25:38)

The flash back sequence shows that the discrimination happens in every situation, Wheeler and Walter are Andrew partners in the firm. And from that dialogues in flashback sequence that is the main reason why Andrew postpones talking about his sexual orientation to his boss. He was afraid that his partners would treat him bad. He felt relieved when he heard their jokes.

3.3. The Struggle against Discrimination

In struggling against discrimination, Andrew has some difficulties. The difficulties that Andrew has are as follows:

3.3.1. To prove the discrimination

Wheeler : Highline Incorporated is now represented by Wyant, Wheeler, Hellerman, Tetlow and Brown, or more specifically, senior associate Andrew Beckett.

Andrew : Kenneth, thank you.

Kenton : You bet, Andy. Congratulations. What's that on your forehead Andy?

Andre : Oh, I got whacked in the head with a racket ball.

(Office, 00:10:28-00:10:34)

The quotation above takes a place in Charles Wheeler office. In that room are Charles, Kenton and Andrew making conversations about the case of Highline Incorporation. It shows that Charles asked Andrew to handle an important client, Highline Incorporation, representing Charles Wheeler law firm. Andrew's struggle starts when he is promoted to be senior associate in handling an important client, Highline Incorporated. And when Kenton congratulates Andrew. He asks what bruise on Andrew's forehead. After see that bruise, Kenton seemed suspicious of Andrew.

In 9 days later after he is promoted as senior associate. When he is in the hospital, his partner beeps him and he quickly makes phone calls to his office. His partner informed him that the highline files that he did last night are missing from his desk. Here is the supporting scene:

Jamey : Andy?! This is a disaster! We can't find the revisions on the Highline complaint!

Andrew : Wait, wait. Slow down.

Jamey : Ok, I told them you've been working on it at home, and it was supposed to be here this morning.

Andrew : I brought it in the office last night. I was there 3 AM; there should be a copy with correction on my desk.

Jamey : I'm telling you it's not here, Andy. Shelby cannot find it either.

Andrew : The hard disk on my computer.

Jamey : What file then?

Andrew : K-R-O-one.

Jamey : It's not here, Andy.

(Hospital, 00:18:05-00:18:58)

The conversation above shows that Andrew asks Jamey to check the backup files from the hard disk of his computer but Jamey cannot find it because the backup has been erased. We can see that not only the correction copies that missing but also the data on Andrew's hard disk in his computer. Andrew was working on the Highline case at home after he is promoted by Wheeler as senior associate because AIDS virus already spreads wider against his body immune which made him weak.

After the incident of the missing files, Charles Wheeler who is Andrew's boss fired him because he was no longer a good lawyer; he is incompetent, having poor work performance and problem with his attitude. That can be proven in the scene below:

Andrew : Excuse me... Am I being fired?

Wheeler : Let's we put it this way, Andy. Your place in the future of this firm is no longer secure. We feel it isn't fair to keep you here when your prospects are limited.

(Office, 00:25:25-00:25:30)

For Wheeler, the missing files accident made him feel that Andrew is incompetent on his work which means that it no longer brings a good fortune for his law firm. The other reasons for Wheeler to fire Andrew is because he believes in Andrew to have an attitude problem in his office. Here is the scene that support the statement above:

Kenton : Some people think you have an attitude problem, Beckett.

Andrew : Really? Who thinks that, Sir?

Wheeler : I do.

(Office, 00:25:08-00:25:15)

From the dialogue above it is clearly seen that Andrew's partners tries to give other reason to fire Andrew. On the other hands, Andrew believes that his boss has sabotaged him about the Highline missing files that made him being fired from his job. This is the supporting scene where Andrew is in Joe's office and told the story about, he was being fired:

Andrew : I misplaced an important complaint. The night before it was due, I worked on the complaint in my office. I left a copy of it on my desk. The next day, the complaint vanished. No hard copy. All traces of it mysteriously gone from my computer. Miraculously, a copy of the complaint was located at the last minute. And we got it to court on time. But the next day I was summoned to meeting with the managing partners. They were waiting for me in the conference room. And I was fired.

Joe : And then...

Andrew : From the day they hired me to the day I was fired...I served my clients consistently, thoroughly, with absolute excellence. If they hadn't fired me, that's what I'd be doing today.

Joe : And they don't want to fire you because for having AIDS. So. In spite of your brilliance, they make you look incompetent. Thus, the mysterious lost files. Is that what you're trying to tell me?

Andrew : Correct. I was sabotaged.

(Joe's office, 00:22:53-00:26:55)

From the dialogues above Andrew tells Joe about the accident of the missing files that he has finished. He wants to sue his office because he believes that he is fired because he is infected AIDS. It is clearly seen that Andrew's boss fired him because they were afraid of AIDS and they sabotaged Andrew with the lost file that they had planned and it became the reason to fire Andrew.

And there is a scene in the movie that supports the discrimination law. The scene takes place in the library when Andrew met Joe. The dialogue of the scene is as the following:

Joe : The Federal Vocational Rehabilitation Act of 1973 prohibits discrimination against otherwise qualified handicapped persons who are able to perform the duties required by their employment... although the rules didn't address the specific issue of HIV and AIDS discrimination.

Andrew : Subsequent decisions have held that AIDS is protected as a handicap under law, not only because of the physical limitations it imposes but because the prejudice surrounding AIDS exacts a social death because which precedes the actual, physical one.”

Joe : This is the essence of discrimination: formulating opinions about others not based on their individual merits, but, rather, on their membership in group with assumed characteristics.
(Library, 00:35:56-00:36:58)

The dialogue explains that AIDS victim is protected by the law because of their physical limitations and people prejudiced around them are the same as the prejudiced handicapped people. The law protects them from the discrimination and violence of the people who have homophobia or hates them. Andrew used that law statement to sue his boss who fired him because of his illness.

Andrew’s basic suspicion is based on his discovering of a female worker of his boss, Melissa Benedict, who has the same scar with Andrew that caused by AIDS. Even though she has AIDS, she is still working until now. Her boss did not fire her. It can be seen from the dialogue below:

Joe : How do you get from one lawyer spotting a lesion, which could have been a bruise, to the partners deducing you had AIDS and basing a decision to terminate you on that conclusion?

Andrew : The partner, who spotted the lesion, Walter Kenton, used to work with Walsh, Ulmer and Bram in D.C there’s a paralegal there, Melissa Benedict. She’s had lesions on and off for three years. She says it was common knowledge around the office that her lesions were caused by AIDS.”

Joe : They didn’t fire her?

Andrew : No, they did not fire her.

(Library, 00:36:01-00:37:02)

Melissa Benedict did not hide the scar of AIDS. It made Andrew feel sure that the scar on his forehead is recognized by his boss. And there is a supporting scene below which Joe asked Andrew whether he has the similar scar when his boss suspected he had AIDS.

Joe : May I borrow your mirror, please? Andrew, do you have any lesions on any part of your body at this time that resembles the lesions you had on your face at the time you were fired?

Andrew : Yes, on my tor... torso.

Joe : On the torso. If it please the court, I would like to ask Mr. Beckett to remove his shirt so that everyone here can have an accurate idea of what we’re talking about.

Judge : I’ll allow it. Mr. Beckett, would you please remove your shirt?

Joe : Andrew, can you see the lesions on your chest in this mirror?

Andrew : Yes.

(Court room, 01:33:29-01:35:01)

The dialogue above takes Andrew as a witness, Joe borrows a mirror from his rival lawyer. Joe asked Andrew whether he has the similar scar when his boss suspected he had AIDS. With the permission of the judge, Joe asked Andrew to remove his shirt and with the mirror asked him if he can see his own scar on his chest or not. With confidence Andrew answered “Yes”.

Based on the evidence above, Joe believes that this case is not only about AIDS but also public’s fear and homosexual’s hate. Here is the supporting scene:

Joe : ... Because this case is not just about AIDS, is it? So let’s talk about what this case is really all about, the general public’s hatred, our loathing, our fear of homosexuals, and how that climate of hatred and fear translated into the firing of this particular homosexual, my client, Andrew Beckett.”

Judge : Please have a seat, Mr. Miller. Very good, in this courtroom, Mr. Miller, justice is blind to matters of race, creed, color, religion and sexual orientation.

(Court room, 01:03:42-01:04:00)

From the dialogues above, Joe is assuring judge that not just about AIDS but about the general public's hatred, the fear of homosexual that makes Andrew being fired. And the judge agrees of Joe's statement that justice is blind to matters of race, creed, color, religion and sexual orientation. It is clearly seen that Andrew is facing two discriminations those are discrimination of AIDS and discrimination of gay that makes him being fired by his boss in the office.

In the final trial, Andrew suspicion is proven based on Mr. Seidman's statement in the trial. He said that he had suspected if Andrew contracted AIDS and was afraid of it. He never talks about it to anyone. The quotation is:

Joe : Mr. Seidman, what did you think to have caused these changes in Andy's appearance?

Seidman : I was afraid. I suspected Andy had AIDS.

Joe : Mr. Seidman, did you share your suspicion with Mr. Wheeler or any of the other managing partners any time before the decision to fire Andrew Beckett was made?

Seidman : No, no, I didn't mention it to anyone, not even Andy. I didn't even give him a chance to talk about it. And I think I'm going to regret that for as long as I live.

(Court room, 01:40:19-01:40:59)

Mr. Seidman is Andrew's partner in the firm. In the dialogues above, from Mr. Seidman's confession that he suspected Andrew had AIDS made Andrew win the trial because Andrew's complaint was proven. Another similar event happened after Wheeler received pursuit letter from Andrew. The scene is as the following:

Wheeler : Wait a minute. The man was fired for incompetence, not because he has AIDS. You didn't know he was sick, did you, Bob?

Kenton : Holy Shit. Did you, Bob?

Seidman : No, not really.

(Office, 00:40:30-00:40:59)

The conversation above happens after Wheeler received pursuit letter from Andrew. Wheeler asks Seidman whether he knows that Andrew has AIDS or not. From the dialogue above, it makes clear that Seidman knows that Andrew is an AIDS victim, but Wheeler and Kenton did not know about it.

Finally, Andrew won the discrimination lawsuit against his ex-employer. He gets damages awarded. It can be seen from the dialogue below.

Judge : Have you awarded any damages?

Juror : Yes, your honor, we have. For back pay and loss of benefits we award \$143,000. For mental anguish and humiliation, we award \$100,000. For punitive damages we award \$4,782,000.

(Court room, 01:42:25-01:42:43)

Andrew won the discrimination lawsuit against his ex-employer. He gets damages awarded from the jurors.

3.3.2. Getting a lawyer

Joe : How many lawyers did you got to, before you called me?

Andrew : Nine.

(Joe's Office, 00:23:24-00:23:29)

From the dialogue above Andrew facing his problem, Andrew tries so hard to find a lawyer to suing Charles Wheeler in the court. All lawyers that he has come in are refuse him. One of the examples is Joe. Joe is the last hope that Andrew has to represent him in the court. But with reasons that he does not see any case on Andrew's story. Joe refused Andrew in suing Charles Wheeler. It can be seen from the scene below:

Joe : I know you were going to say that. I don't buy it, and I don't see a case.
Andrew : Look. I know I have a case. If you don't want to take it for personal reasons...
Joe : Correct I don't.

(Joe's office, 00:34:02:00:34:18)

Dialogue above shows Andrew tried to convince Joe, but Joe still rejected him. Joe didn't believe in Andrew's story. The truth he rejected Andrew's case because he was afraid of AIDS virus.

Although there was no lawyer that supported him in the trial, he still maintained his will to get his right and looking for some data about discrimination in the library. Then Andrew is discriminated by a librarian and Joe is in that library too and sees that accident. Here is the scene.

Librarian : This is the supplement. You're right, there is a section on... HIV related discrimination.
Andrew : Thank you.
Librarian : We do have a private research room available.
Andrew : I'm fine right here, thank you.
Librarian : Wouldn't you be more comfortable in a research room?
Andrew : No, would it make you more comfortable?
Joe : Hi Andrew... Do you find a lawyer?

(Library, 00:31:40-00:34:45)

The dialogue takes place in the library when Andrew was studying his own case(making important notes that supported his case). A librarian forced Andrew to move to private room and immediately Joe comes over to Andrew.

From that accident Joe feels empathetic with him for the discriminatory that happened in the library. It made him change his mind and he decided to take Andrew's case and helped him to sue Charles Wheeler. Then they are looking for data about discrimination together.

3.3.3. Relieve from AIDS

Dr. Klenstein : It's not a pleasant procedure, but if the KS is causing the diarrhea, we've got to know about that right away.
Miguel : It could be parasites, an infection...
Andrew : A reaction to AZT...
Dr. Klenstein : That's possible, but.
Miguel : He's not going through some painful procedure until we've cancelled out everything else.

(Hospital, 00:16:27-00:16:58)

The conversation happens when Andrew with his lover Miguel in the hospital meets Dr. Kleinstein. And the doctor tells Andrew about the treatment. The treatment caused Andrew diarrhea and sometimes it can be painful.

There is no medicine to cure AIDS virus. Only by routine treatment people can survive from the virus. Andrew used kinds of treatment to prolong his life. Some treatment brings various affects to the patient. There is a supporting scene that shows Andrew's lover tries to help Andrew to get over from AIDS.

Miguel : The vein's closed. We have to call Barbara to tell her to come over.
Andrew : I have too much work to do. Skip the treatment.

Miguel : We're not skipping this treatment.

(Andrew's house, 01:07:40-01:07:49)

From the dialogue above it can be seen that Andrew's lover tried to put on infuse to Andrew's arms. But the vein is closed so he wants to call Barbara a nurse at Andrew's hospital. Andrew wants to skip the treatment because of his work for the trial.

It is clearly seen that Andrew's struggle against his illness, he must do the treatment regularly. In spite of the fact that he could not survive from HIV virus.

IV. DISCUSSION

After analyzing the discrimination of Andrew Beckett, the researchers get result. The result is related to sociological perspective because sociology is a general science that studies about certain aspects of human interaction and activity and human life. There are two perspective of sociology that relates to the discrimination of Andrew Beckett those are Conflict theory and functionalism.

4.1. Conflict Theory

According to (Laluddin, 2016) stated that "Conflict Theory presents a different picture of society. It depicts society as an arena of wide spread conflict and struggle at every level of it. And use the power to play the role". Discrimination of Andrew Beckett is related to the conflict theory. There are some conflicts such as conflict between the law firm and Andrew Beckett. In the beginning of the movie the law firm held the social power and fired Andrew Beckett based on diagnosis of AIDS and his homosexuality because the law firm held the power.

The last is the law firm had fear of Andrew Beckett due to his homosexuality and his diagnosis of AIDS. At the end of the film Andrew Beckett won the discrimination lawsuit against his ex-employer. So, Andrew Beckett held the power.

4.2. Functionalism

According to (College, 2013) "In the view of functionalism must have served an important function in order to exist as long as it has. This concept, of course, is problematic. How can discrimination contribute positively to society? Sociologists who adhere to the functionalist view argue that discrimination does contribute positively, but only to the dominant group.

In this movie the dominant group is the Law firm. In the beginning of the story the law firm held the social power and fired Andrew Beckett based on diagnosis of AIDS and his homosexuality because the law firm held the power. Thus, discrimination of Andrew Beckett does contribute positively for the law firm.

V. CONCLUSION

Andrew Beckett is a protagonist character who wants to gain his right and he is a good guy. Andrew Beckett is an excellent lawyer in the law firm but he is discriminated by his partners therefore he hires a lawyer to pursue his office and get his rights in the trial. To get his right he hires a lawyer to help her in the trial. Andrew also loves his family who support him in facing his problem. In facing his problem, Andrew is a patient character.

There are some discriminations against Andrew Beckett in this movie those are discrimination of AIDS and gay. The discrimination happens in every place. In this movie, the discrimination happens in the social services area and in the work place. Andrew Beckett is one of the examples of a person who is discriminated because he is gay and he is infected with the HIV virus that causes his AIDS. In the social service area, Andrew is avoided by people around him and in the work place; his boss fires him from his job. In struggling against the discrimination, Andrew has some difficulties. He has to prove the discrimination. He tries to hire many attorneys to suing Charles Wheeler in the court. All lawyers that he has come in are refuse him. The last hope is Joe Miller but he refuses to take the case until finally he sees the discriminatory act against Andrew that

happened in the library. From that accident Joe feels empathetic with him it made him change his mind and he decided to take Andrew's case and helped him to sue Charles Wheeler. Andrew also must fight against his illness. He has to get over from AIDS to undergo court proceedings. In spite of the fact that Andrew won the trial, he could not survive from HIV virus. He died few days after the final trial.

The discrimination of Andrew Beckett is related to sociological perspective because sociology is a general science that studies about certain aspects of human interaction and activity and human life. There are two perspective of sociology that relates to the discrimination of Andrew Beckett those are Conflict theory and functionalism.

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